

Canterbury Tales Project Newsletter 1 (August 1993).

This document has been reconstructed from the original Adobe Pagemaker (.pm5) and Microsoft Word files used in making the first newsletter. The original files are no longer readable, and this document has been created by retrieving the text from those files. Thus, there will be differences between this document and the original newsletter.

Editorial

This is the first newsletter of the Canterbury Tales Project. This Project aims to make available over a ten-year period full transcripts of the text of every manuscript and pre-1500 printed edition of the *Canterbury Tales*, together with computer images of every page of every manuscript and early edition, collations of all these texts, and analyses of the textual tradition based on the transcripts. Cambridge University Press is to publish these materials in CD-ROM form in a new Cambridge Electronic Editions series, commencing in late 1994 with the fifty-five manuscripts and four pre-1500 printed editions of the Wife of Bath's Prologue.

This newsletter introduces the aims, methods, and staff of the Canterbury Tales Project. Overleaf, we sketch who we are and how we are funded. Other articles outline the system of transcription and of presentation of the manuscript images, the method of collation, and the techniques of computer-assisted analysis of the history of the tradition. Finally we explain how we might make all this material manageable to other scholars and describe the first volume of Project *Occasional Papers*.

We are distributing this first newsletter free, to let as many people as possible know what we are doing. Our funding is limited and future numbers of the newsletter will be available by subscription. The first *Occasional Papers* volume and a year's subscription to future numbers of the newsletter will be available for £10 UK for Europe, \$20 US for elsewhere in the world. Subscription to the newsletter alone (after the first free copy, and without *Occasional Papers* volumes) is available, at £4 UK, \$8 US including postage per annual two issues. There is a subscription slip on the last page.

Who we are and how we are funded

The Project Director, Professor Norman Blake, is head of the department of English Language and Linguistics at the University of Sheffield. He has edited the *Canterbury Tales* from the Hengwrt manuscript and has published widely on the textual tradition of the *Canterbury Tales*.

The Executive Officer, Dr. Peter Robinson, is based at the Office for Humanities Communication, an agency sponsored by the British Library Research and Development Division and directed by Dr Marilyn Deegan. Dr Robinson has edited Old Norse poetic texts, is the developer of Collate, a widely-used collation program, and is head of the Text Encoding Initiative work-group on Textual Criticism.

The Principal Transcriber, Ms Elizabeth Solopova, is a graduate of the University of Moscow. She is currently a doctoral student at St Hilda's College Oxford and is writing a thesis on the prosody of Middle English verse before Chaucer.

To be successful, the Project must draw on the skills and experience of other medievalists. We have benefited greatly from the advice of Dr Malcolm Parkes and Professors Anne Hudson, Eric Stanley, and Malcolm Godden in Oxford, and from discussions with members of the Early Book Society, following the first formal presentation of the project at their July 1993 conference in Sheffield. Through this newsletter and the *Occasional Papers*, we hope for further response concerning what we are doing and how we are doing it.

The beginnings of the Canterbury Tales Project lie in the experimental transcription of some manuscripts of the Wife of Bath's Prologue during the Computers and Manuscripts Project, based in Oxford University Computing Services between 1989 and 1992. The aim of this transcription was to provide materials for testing the computer collation program Collate, then under development, and for exploring methods of computer-assisted stemmatic analysis. This work showed up serious deficiencies in the analysis of Manly and Rickert and also suggested that computer techniques might permit more exact and comprehensive analysis. Over the same period, advances in computer handling of images and their

distribution in CD-ROM form indicated that images of all the manuscripts might be made available also. These factors led to the inauguration of this Project.

The first part of the Canterbury Tales Project, consisting of the Wife of Bath's Prologue, has received support from the Universities of Oxford and Sheffield, the Leverhulme Trust, and the British Academy. Funding is being negotiated for later parts of the Project.

The transcripts and the images

We aim to transcribe the text of all the manuscripts and selected early printed editions. The original spelling of the witnesses will be preserved in the transcriptions. All abbreviations and possibly significant marks in the witnesses will be represented without expansion. Scribal deletions, additions, and underlinings will be recorded, as will manuscript punctuation and other structural marking. All glosses will, in time, also be transcribed.

If the transcripts are to be useful as a corpus of information on fifteenth- and sixteenth-century language, it is vital that they be consistent. The first volume of *Occasional Papers* contains a statement of transcription principles, and we welcome comment on this.

Each transcript will be checked at least three times. Where possible, at least one of these checks will be against the manuscript. An accuracy of no more than one error per three thousand characters (approximately one error per fifty manuscript lines) will be sought.

Each transcription will be available both in unregularized form, preserving all original spellings, and in regularized form, enabling substantive comparison of readings across the witnesses. The first volume of *Occasional Papers* will contain a statement of the guidelines for the manuscript transcription.

The Project will publish, subject to obtaining necessary permissions, at least one computer image of every page of every manuscript or early printed edition of the *Canterbury Tales*. Most of the images will be derived by high-resolution digital scan of microfilm copies of the witnesses purchased by the Project. These images will be binary (i.e. plain black and white) scans, with resolution equating to between 200 and 300 dpi of the original.

Where possible, the Project will provide colour images of manuscripts. Some colour images will be derived by the Kodak Photo CD process. These images will be 24 bit colour (i.e. a choice of 16.7 million colours), with resolution equating to between 150 and 250 dpi of the original witness. We hope that other colour images may be made by digital photography direct from the manuscripts themselves.

The collation

The Project will produce collations of all the witnesses in both unregularized and regularized forms. The unregularized collation will present all the variational information about the witnesses, both non-substantive and substantive. The regularized collation will remove non-substantive variation by regularizing out (for example) manuscript abbreviations, punctuation, and differing verbal forms. Collations of smaller groups of the witnesses will also be provided, again in both unregularized and regularized forms.

All collations will be produced using the computer program *Collate*, developed specifically for the collation of medieval vernacular texts. Accordingly, it contains powerful regularization facilities. The practice of the Hengwrt manuscript will be used as a base for all regularizations done within the program.

A version of *Collate* will be provided on the CD-ROM (likely to be Macintosh version only, for the first releases). Scholars will be able to use this to make collations of their own using different selections of manuscripts, or using different master texts, or to make their own editions, or in teaching about the making of editions. They may also adjust the regularization of the manuscripts using *Collate*.

The analyses

Spellings

As part of the regularization process, *Collate* creates a complete record of every regularization it does of every word (or group of words, in the case of word division). The regularization records created by the various collations will be output to spelling databases and distributed on the CD-ROM.

The spelling databases will permit all the variant forms in them to be sorted, counted, and viewed side by side. Correlation of the distribution of different forms with known facts about the provenance of individual manuscripts or of the geographical and historical distribution of particular forms may be used to advance knowledge both about the manuscripts themselves and about the linguistic and dialectical variation they contain.

The spelling databases on the CD-ROM of the Wife of Bath's Prologue will contain information about the forms of some two hundred thousand words in the witnesses. The complete Project will contain information about some five million word forms.

Manuscript transmission: cladistics

The principal reason for exploration of the textual tradition of *the Canterbury Tales* is to try to discover what Chaucer actually wrote. An essential step in this process is recovery of the history of the development of the tradition. The recent application of methods of computer analysis to the reconstruction of the history of textual traditions suggests that computer-aided techniques may succeed where traditional manual methods may not.

Notable among these computer methods is cladistic analysis. This is a technique developed in evolutionary biology to reconstruct the 'family tree' of related species by study of the characteristics they share and do not share. The success of cladistic analysis, working from manuscripts agreements and disagreements on particular words as generated by *Collate*, has been demonstrated on a variety of texts, particularly the forty-six manuscripts of the Old Norse narrative sequence *Svipdagsmál*. Experimental work on the Wife of Bath's Prologue manuscripts has shown the power of cladistic analysis for rapid creation of views of manuscript relations which can guide further research.

Variant databases

Cladistic analysis cannot, of itself, explain exactly how each and every witness is related. It can suggest that there might be a relationship between certain witnesses but cannot determine just what the relationship is: whether descent from a common exemplar, or one from another. Cladistic analysis may also be misled by contamination or other lateral transmission into thinking that manuscripts are rather more closely related than they are.

In order to determine exactly how manuscripts are related one needs ready access to the variants themselves which evidence a relationship. For example, in pursuing the relationship between Hengwrt (Hg), Ellesmere (El), and Harleian 7334 (Ha4) one needs answers to questions like 'what variants are found in El and in Ha4, and in no more than three other manuscripts, but not in Hg'.

To provide rapid answers to such questions, we will use variant databases of all the variants in all the manuscripts, both in regularized and unregularized forms. *Collate* has a variant database search tool which we are testing before its general release. This tool can answer questions like that asked above in around one or two seconds: in the manuscripts we have transcribed, there are twenty-four variants in both El and Ha4, not in Hg, and in no more than three other manuscripts.

All these analytic tools will be provided on the CD-ROM, together with discussions of the results of our use of them. The first volume of *Occasional Papers* will contain an article by Peter Robinson and Robert O'Hara discussing cladistic analysis.

The electronic edition

The first Canterbury Tales Project CD-ROM will contain transcripts of the fifty-five manuscripts and the four pre-1500 printed editions of the Wife of Bath's Prologue and computer images (subject to the necessary permissions) of all eleven hundred pages of these manuscripts and editions. It will also contain full collations and analyses of the manuscript relations of the Prologue, in both regularized and unregularized forms, databases of spellings and variants, and (for the Macintosh version) collation and analytic software.

Making all this material accessible and easily usable will be a considerable challenge. The computer interface will be based on that of *Collate*, with manuscript images, transcripts, collation, and analytic tools available through a Macintosh-style 'graphical user interface'. Text, images, etc., will appear in multiple

windows (so that images and transcripts may be studied alongside one another); tools will be invoked by pointing with the mouse or selecting from menus.

The first aim of the interface will be to allow scholars to check the exact support for any reading as quickly as possible. Typically, users will see first a lightly-edited master text. They will be able to find the line they are interested in, press the mouse on a particular word and the regularized collation of all the witnesses for that word will appear in a window. Clicking once on a manuscript sigil in the collation window will bring up the whole of the transcript of that manuscript, open at that particular point in another screen window. Clicking twice on the sigil will open an image of that page of that manuscript in yet another screen window. Then, one may use the collation and analytic tools to carry out one's own collation of this line, or analyse the agreements between manuscripts.

The cost of the first CD-ROM has not yet been fixed. We are concerned that that the price of each CD-ROM should be within the reach of research libraries and of committed individual scholars. We would expect the cost for a single CD-ROM to be more comparable to the cost of a printed scholarly critical edition (with the volumes of CUP's D. H. Lawrence retailing at around £75 UK, \$100 US) than to the cost of, for example, Chadwyck-Healey CD-ROMs.

The Occasional Papers

In December 1993 we intend to publish, in the Office for Humanities Communication publication series, the first volume of Canterbury Tales Project *Occasional Papers*. As the title suggests, this is intended more as a record of work-in-progress, or an outline of work-to-be-done, than as a final repository for definitive work which might be better published in monograph form or in an established journal. The focus of the *Occasional Papers* will be the study of the manuscripts and of the early printed editions of the *Canterbury Tales*. However, this will not preclude items dealing with related areas (other Middle English manuscript traditions, etc.) where these raise relevant issues, and we welcome suggestions about articles concerning these as well as those relating specifically to the *Canterbury Tales*. In keeping with the occasional nature of these papers, we aim to produce each volume as quickly as possible, and to keep costs down by doing the production and distribution ourselves.

At the time of writing (August 1993), we have not settled the exact contents of the first volume of *Occasional Papers*. We expect that it will contain articles by Norman Blake (concerning the background to the Project and its place in the context of *Canterbury Tales* textual scholarship), Peter Robinson and Elizabeth Solopova (the guidelines for the manuscript transcription), Robert O'Hara (the principles, techniques and application of cladistic analysis; with Peter Robinson), Stephen Partridge (the glosses within the textual tradition), and Dan Mosser (cataloguing the manuscripts of the *Canterbury Tales*). [There is a subscription slip below.]